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Global Marketing Adaptation Strategies And Business Success Of Cassava Processing Firms In Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between marketing strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. Five (5) objectives, five (5) research questions and five (5) hypotheses were formulated. The research adopted a descriptive survey design, and the population of the study comprised 3 cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt, Rivers State namely: Rivers Cassava Processing Company Ltd; Uzere Cassava Processing Factory; and Premium Cassava Product Limited. Sequel to the population of the study, which is 3 cassava processing firms, the study adopted a census study with a focus on the managers in the firms. To generate data for the study, the questionnaire was distributed in batches of ten (10) copies per firm. A total of thirty (30) copies of the questionnaire were distributed. Copies of the questionnaire were administered and distributed to the respondents of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. The study employed the Spearman Rank-Order Correlational Coefficient and partial correlation for testing the various hypotheses formulated for the study with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The result of the analysis revealed that there is significant relationship between product adaptation and repeat purchase and customer loyalty and there is significant relationship between promotional adaptation and repeat purchase and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. This study concluded that global marketing adaptation strategies (product adaptation and promotional adaptation) has a positive and significant relationship with repeat purchase and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. In view of the findings, the study recommends that cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt should adapt their products to the local market so as to drive its products and services to the target market and to further improve the firm's level of patronage and Promotional adaptation should be put into consideration so as to increase product awareness to consumers.

Keywords: Global marketing adaptation, Product adaptation, promotional adaptation, business success, share growth, market share growth

INTRODUCTION

Globally, businesses that tailor products to match local tastes, cultural norms, and consumption habits outperform competitors that adopt standardized offerings. For instance, multinational firms in food processing industries routinely adapt packaging sizes, nutritional content, and branding to align with local demand. Studies have shown that such adaptations significantly increase consumer satisfaction, brand loyalty, and ultimately, market share growth (Cavusgil et al., 2021). The cassava industry, a vital part of global Agri-food systems, exemplifies the potential for market-driven growth. The global cassava market

was valued at USD 815.64 million in 2024, and is projected to grow to over USD 1.66 billion by 2033—driven by increased demand for convenience foods, gluten-free ingredients, and bio-based industrial applications (Straits Research, 2025). Cassava starch alone represents a USD 5.45 billion market as of 2023, projected to grow steadily due to its use in textiles, food, and pharmaceuticals (GlobeNewswire, 2025). Nigeria is the world’s largest producer of cassava, accounting for approximately 20% of global cassava output, with an estimated annual production of 59 million tons (Farmvilla, 2025). However, while production figures are strong, market penetration and commercial value addition remain weak—particularly among small and medium-scale processing firms in regions like Port Harcourt. The challenge lies not in the quantity produced, but in how cassava products are positioned in the market. Many firms lack the strategic marketing competencies to adapt their products and promotional messages to fit consumer expectations. This limits their ability to increase market share, even in an environment where demand is rising.

A deeper issue is the failure of many firms to view market share growth as a strategic performance metric tied directly to marketing agility. When firms successfully implement adaptation strategies—such as modifying cassava flour granulation for regional dishes, or designing culturally resonant branding—they unlock pathways to sustainable growth, profitability, and competitive advantage (Day, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

Despite the increasing importance of cassava as both a food security crop and a raw material for industrial processing in Nigeria, particularly in the Niger Delta region, many cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt continue to experience limited market penetration and stagnating sales growth. This underperformance persists despite growing urban demand, and technological advancements in value addition.

A major contributing factor is the inadequate alignment between marketing strategies and consumer expectations in the local context. Many of these firms fail to sufficiently adapt their products to meet diverse local taste preferences, packaging expectations, and quality standards. Similarly, promotional strategies are often poorly localized, relying on generic or non-targeted campaigns that fail to resonate with rural and semi-urban consumers. This gap creates a strategic blind spot for firm managers, policymakers, and development agencies seeking to stimulate inclusive agribusiness growth. Without a clear understanding of how localized marketing adaptations drive commercial success, efforts to scale the cassava value chain may fall short, leading to inefficiencies, poor competitiveness, and missed opportunities for rural industrialization. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework shows the relationship between the predictor (global marketing adaptation strategies) and criterion (business success) variable.

Figure 1.1: Conceptual framework showing the relationship between global marketing adaptation and business success.

Sources: Adekola (2021); Adewale et., al., (2013); Azra & Ummah (2021).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. The specific objectives of this study are as follows:

- i. ascertain the relationship between product adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- ii. determine the relationship between product adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- iii. examine the relationship between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- iv. evaluate the relationship between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- v. determine the extent to which corporate image moderate the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Research Questions

The following research questions were postulated to address the objectives of the study:

- i. What is the relationship between product adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt?

- ii. What is the relationship between product adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt?
- iii. What is the relationship between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt?
- iv. What is the relationship between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt?
- v. How does corporate image moderate the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide this study:

- Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between product adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between product adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- Ho₅: Corporate image does not significant moderate the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Concept of Global marketing adaptation strategies

Global marketing adaptation strategies refers to the process of modifying marketing strategies and practices to suit the unique needs, preferences, and cultural differences of diverse international markets. It involves tailoring product offerings, promotional campaigns, pricing strategies, and distribution channels to accommodate local market conditions while maintaining brand consistency and global standards (Cavusgil et al., 2014). To Jeong and Bong (2016) global marketing adaptation strategies is the customization of marketing strategies and tactics by multinational companies to align with local market conditions and consumer behaviors. Global marketing adaptation strategies plays a crucial role in enhancing market penetration, brand relevance, and customer satisfaction across international markets. It allows companies to establish strong connections with local consumers, build brand loyalty, and gain competitive advantage in diverse cultural and economic landscapes (Hollensen, 2021).

Dimensions of Global marketing adaptation strategies

Promotional adaptation

This dimension involves adjusting promotional activities, advertising campaigns, and communication strategies to effectively reach and engage local consumers. Multinational companies may leverage different media channels, messaging styles, and cultural cues to convey brand value propositions and influence consumer behavior in diverse markets. Keegan and Green (2017) stated that promotional adaptation involves tailoring marketing communication strategies to effectively reach target audiences in diverse international markets. This may include adjusting advertising messages, media channels, or promotional campaigns to reflect local language, culture, and consumer behaviors. It refers to the customization of promotional activities and communication strategies to resonate with the unique characteristics and preferences of target markets. This may involve adapting advertising content, slogans, or imagery to align with cultural sensitivities and market nuances (Kotler et al., 2016).

Effective promotional adaptation requires a deep understanding of cultural norms, values, and symbols prevalent in the target market. Marketers must tailor promotional materials to resonate positively with local consumers while avoiding cultural taboos or insensitive portrayals. Adaptation extends to the selection of media channels and platforms used for promotional activities. Different markets may have

varying media consumption habits, requiring marketers to choose appropriate channels (e.g., TV, radio, social media) that maximize reach and impact.

Product Adaptation

This dimension focuses on customizing product features, attributes, and packaging to align with local preferences, cultural norms, and regulatory requirements. Multinational firms may modify product designs, functionalities, or formulations to better resonate with target markets while maintaining brand consistency and quality standards. Kotler and Armstrong (2006) define a product as anything that can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use, or consumption that might satisfy a want or need. They further defined a consumer product as the product bought by the final consumer for personal consumption. Consumers buy products frequently, with careful planning, and by comparing brands based on price, quality and style. Mohammadzadeh et., al., (2013) also say that product is the physical appearance of the product, packaging, and labeling Information, which can also influence whether consumers notice a product in-store, examine it, and purchase it. Past researchers have clearly suggested that product influences have a significant impact on business success (Mustapha, 2017; Nguru et., al., 2017; Langat 2016; Owomoyela et., al., 2013). In marketing, the product is important component of the marketing mix. It determines whether the organization survives or dies. To develop the 'right' product is not an easy task because of the dynamic nature of consumer needs and attitudes. The goods and/or services people buy at any given time are determined by their immediate needs and other external stimuli (Prinka, et., al., 2019).

Concept of Business Success

Business success is "the achievement of predetermined goals and objectives, resulting in financial profitability, growth, and sustainability" (Kuratko & Hodgetts, 2007). This definition highlights that business success is measured by the attainment of specific goals and objectives set by the organization. It emphasizes the importance of financial profitability, growth, and long-term sustainability as indicators of success. Similarly, Thompson and Martin, (2010) defined business success is "the ability of an organization to create and deliver value to its customers, stakeholders, and society, while achieving desired outcomes and maintaining a competitive advantage".

Sales Growth

Sales growth is one of the marketing metric used to measure business success. According to Parida et al (2016), sales growth is the increase in the sales made by a company for a given period of time. Sales growth can be measured periodically such as daily, monthly, quarterly or yearly depending on the type and size of the organization. Micro, small and medium sized firms usually evaluate their sales on a daily, weekly, monthly or quarterly basis while large firms evaluate their sales annually (Gaur & Kesavan, 2015). When a company's sales are increasing from year to year, one can say that the company is experiencing consistent sales growth. Lechner et al (2016) stated that sales growth is achieved when a company's sales for the year under review is higher than the sales made in the previous year. Sales growth is one of the business objectives which every company wants to achieve. According to Sam and Hoshino (2013), every company irrespective of the industry it belongs wants to achieve sales growth. This is because when the sales of a company grows from year to year, the profit margin of the company will grow in the same direction. Gaur and Kesavan (2015) stated that sales growth does not only increase the net profit of a company but also help to position the company in the minds of prospective investors.

Market Share Growth

Market share refers to the portion of the market served or captured by a company in relation to the total market of the overall industry (Kumar & Petersen, 2005). Huynh and Petrunia (2010) defined market share as the percentage or portion of the total market which is controlled by the company. Hence, market share growth is the increase in the portion of the market captured by a company from year to year (McKelvie & Wiklund, 2010). Huynh and Petrunia (2010) stated that market share growth enables a company to attain greater scale of operations and increase its profitability. A higher market share means more sales for the company, lesser effort to sell more products and a

strong discouragement to competitors who are planning to enter the industry. Every company irrespective of its size wants to increase their market share since it is a sure way to maximize profit. To increase market share, companies need to put in more efforts to grow its sales (Brudan, 2010). Akaeze and Akaeze (2017) stated that consistent increase in market share should be the primary goal of every organization and that any organization that does not have market share growth as a primary goal should have re-think. Increasing the market share brings about profit maximization (Li et al, 2008). Companies that are determined to increase their market share usually introduced new products and services in order to stand out among their major competitors (McKelvie & Wiklund, 2010).

Theoretical Review

This study is underpinned by the Resource-Based Theory

The resource-based view (RBV) of the firm argues that competitive advantage – and subsequently performance depends on historically developed resource endowments (Wernerfelt, 1984). Consequently, firms, in particular marketing (Barney, 1991), should build on resources that contribute to their ability to produce valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable market offerings in a manner that is either efficient or effective (Hunt & Morgan, 1995). As Fahy and Smithee (1999) argued, intangible resources and capabilities, such as organizational learning (Santos-Vijande et al., 2005) and customer knowledge (Webster, 1992) are especially difficult to duplicate and thus, provide a meaningful basis for marketing strategies like place and price strategies. As such, intangible resources and capabilities have the potential to become distinctive competencies for the firm (Blois & Ramirez, 2006). There is evidence in practice and academic research that firm competencies and resources are key factors of assessing a firm's future value potential (Möller & Törrönen, 2003) and, thus, supplier selection in business markets (Golfetto & Gibbert, 2006). According to Ritter (2006), this refers to process and market competencies in particular (routines related to the properties and characteristics of the firm's value-creation process and the value transfer between the firm and its environment). There has been an emerging discussion within marketing research, as originated by Kohli and Jaworski (1990) and Narver and Slater (1990), on the effects market strategy on business performance (Kaynak & Kara, 2004). However, much remains unsettled, while the same applies to contextual moderation of performance with regard to other marketing phenomena (Barney, 1991).

Empirical Review

Ogohi (2018) conducted a research on the Effects of Marketing Strategies on Organizational Performance. The purpose of the study was to investigate the effects of Marketing Strategies on Organizational Performance; A Study of Nigeria Bottling Company Kaduna, including Production strategy, promotional adaptation, promotion strategy and place strategy, that eventually influences Marketing strategies on performance. Marketing strategy has been a focus of organizations and a tool for attaining overall firm performance. The study contributed to the existing study of marketing strategy by supporting a relationship between marketing strategy factors and overall firm performance. For price specifically, the study found a positive and significant effect on performance of the firms.

Al-Mamun, et., al., (2014) carried out a Critical Review of Consumers' Sensitivity to Price: Managerial and Theoretical Issues. Consumers' price sensitivity is an important input to strategic and tactical decisions. Price sensitivities depend on various factors for which the purpose of the paper was to explore consumers' price sensitivity and innovativeness as well as to contribute to diffusion theory by adding information on price sensitivity. The research reviewed how consumers demonstrate their sensitivities to price on their product purchase decisions. From quantitative analysis methods, the study found a significant effect of price on customers buying behavior.

Azra and Ummah (2021) examined the impact of marketing strategies on growth of small and medium enterprises. The study adopted the survey method among 114 SMEs within the Central Province. The data obtained was analysed using validity test, reliability test, descriptive analysis, correlation analysis and regression analysis with the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0. The study revealed that there is a significant impact of marketing strategies on business growth of SMEs. The study

recommends that SMEs should concern more on marketing mix strategy, Ansoff matrix and porter's generic theory in marketing strategies to improve the growth of the business. Findings showed that adjusted R2 of Marketing Strategies is 0.879. Therefore, 87.9% of variation in Business growth explained by marketing strategies. This study facilitates to SMEs and policy makers to implement efficient policies the successful business growth.

METHODOLOGY

The research adopted a descriptive survey design, and the population of the study comprised 3 cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt, Rivers State namely: Rivers Cassava Processing Company Ltd; Uzere Cassava Processing Factory; and Premium Cassava Product Limited gotten from <https://www.google.com/search?q=list+of+cassava+processing+companies+>. Sequel to the population of the study, which is 3 cassava processing firms, the study adopted a census study with a focus on the managers in the firms. To generate data for the study, the questionnaire was distributed in batches of ten (10) copies per firm. A total of thirty (30) copies of the questionnaire were distributed. Copies of the questionnaire were administered and distributed to the respondents of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. The study employed the Spearman Rank-Order Correlational Coefficient for testing the various hypotheses formulated for the study with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 27.0.

PRESENTATION OF DATA AND ANALYSIS

Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval

No. of Questionnaire Issued	No. of Questionnaire Returned	Useful Questionnaire	Not Useful	%
30	26	26	-	86

Source; survey Data, 2025.

The table above shows the questionnaire distribution and retrieval. The researcher issued 30 copies of questionnaire and from consistent visit, retrieved 26, 26 copies were useful. This represent 86% response rate and it was considered significant for the study.

Bivariate Analyses

Test of Hypothesis one (1)

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between product adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

		Correlations		
			product adaptation	sales growth
Spearman's rho	product adaptation	Correlation	1.000	.905**
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.002
		N	26	26
	sales growth	Correlation	.905**	1.000
		Coefficient		
Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	.	
	N	26	26	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

SPSS output, 2025.

The output analyzed the extent to which product adaptation relate with sales growth. Spearman's correlation co-efficient indicates a strong association between the two variables (Rs=0.905). The test of significance indicates that with $P.002 < 0.01$ we can reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between product adaptation and sales growth. Thus, we can say that higher levels of product adaptation were associated with higher levels of loyalty in cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Test of Hypothesis two (2)

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between product adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

		Correlations		
			product adaptation	market share growth
Spearman's rho	product adaptation	Correlation	1.000	.762*
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.028
		N	26	26
	market share growth	Correlation	.762*	1.000
		Coefficient		
Sig. (2-tailed)		.028	.	
	N	26	26	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

SPSS output, 2025.

The output analyzed the extent to which product adaptation relates with market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. Spearman's correlation co-efficient indicates a strong association between the two variables (Rs=0.762). The test of significance indicates that with $P.028 < 0.05$ we can reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between product adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. Thus, we can say that higher levels of product adaptation were associated with higher levels of market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Test of Hypothesis three (3)

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Correlations			
		promotional adaptation	sales growth
Spearman's rho	promotional adaptation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.778*
		N	.023
			26
Spearman's rho	sales growth	Correlation Coefficient	.778*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000
		N	.023
			26

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source, Survey Data 2025.

The table above presents the result of correlation analysis between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. The result indicates that there is a strong correlation between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt (rho = .778*) and this correlation is significant at 0.05 level as indicated by the symbol *. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (Ho₃) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is significant relationship between promotional adaptation and sales growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Test of Hypothesis four (4)

Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Correlations			
		Promotional adaptation	market share growth
Spearman's rho	Promotional adaptation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.802*
		N	.017
			26
Spearman's rho	market share growth	Correlation Coefficient	.802*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000
		N	.017
			26

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source, Survey Data 2025.

The table above presents the result of correlation analysis between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. The result indicates that there is a very strong correlation between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt (rho = .802*) and this correlation is significant at 0.05 level as indicated by the symbol *. Based on this result, the null hypothesis (Ho₄) is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is significant relationship between promotional adaptation and market share growth of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Test of Hypothesis five (5)

Ho₅: Corporate image does not significant moderate the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Partial Correlation

Control Variables		global marketing adaptation strategies	business success
	Correlation	1.000	.975*
	Coefficient		
global marketing adaptation strategies	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.017
	N	26	26
Corporate image	Correlation	.975*	1.000
	Coefficient		
business success	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	.
	N	26	26

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS output, 2025.

From the analysis, the result indicates that corporate image significantly moderates the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt ($r = .975^*$) and this correlation is significant at 0.05 level as indicated by the symbol *. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This means that corporate image significantly moderates the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

Summary of Findings

- i. There is a significant relationship between product adaptation and repeat purchase of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- ii. There is a significant relationship between product adaptation and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- iii. There is a significant relationship between promotional adaptation and repeat purchase of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- iv. There is a significant relationship between promotional adaptation and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.
- v. Corporate image significantly moderate the relationship between global marketing adaptation strategies and business success of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the analysis carried out, it was discovered that product adaptation showed a very strong, positive and significant relationship with repeat purchase and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. This finding is in line with the study of Adekola (2021) who assessed the effect of product on performance of manufacturing firms in North Central Nigeria. The study adopted the survey research design to test a sample of 398 respondents from a population of 74,219 management staff of manufacturing firms in North Central Nigeria. Primary data was used for the study and collected through the use of structured five-point Likert scale questionnaire instrument. Multiple regression technique was used to test the research hypotheses. The study found a positive and significant effect of product on performance of the firms as well as a positive and significant effect of price on performance of the manufacturing firms in North Central Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that global marketing adaptation strategies (product adaptation and promotional adaptation) has a positive and significant relationship with repeat purchase and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt. In essence, global marketing adaptation strategies via product adaptation and promotional adaptation are useful tools for improving business success of cassava processing firms. The study revealed that there is significant relationship between product adaptation and repeat purchase and customer loyalty and there is significant relationship between promotional adaptation and repeat purchase and customer loyalty of cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Cassava processing firms in Port Harcourt should adapt their products to the local market so as to drive its products and services to the target market and to further improve the firm's level of patronage.
- ii. Promotional adaptation should be put into consideration so as to increase product awareness to consumers.
- iii. Cassava processing firms should tailor their promotional strategies to resonate with the local audience. This includes using appropriate media channels, local languages, and culturally relevant messages in advertising campaigns.
- iv. Cassava processing firms should invest in building a reputable and trustworthy brand image through consistent quality, reliable customer service, and positive community engagement.

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